

STIFFNESS PROPERTIES OF THREE DIMENSIONALLY (3-D) REINFORCED GLASS FABRICS PRODUCED BY NEEDLE-FELTING

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the influence of a needle-felting textile process on the in-plane and through thickness stiffness properties of glass fibre-reinforced fabrics. It was shown in [1] that the 3-D reinforcement considerably improves the fracture and delamination resistance of the material. In the current investigation the changes in the tensile stiffness in the plane of the laminate and the tensile and shear properties in the thickness direction are quantified in-situ by applying non-destructive evaluation techniques. The results show that the fast and cost effective needle-felting process which results in toughness-optimised, glass fibre-reinforced fabrics does not noticeably affect the in-plane stiffness properties of the laminate.

KEYWORDS: glass fibre-reinforced laminated composite, three dimensional, needle-felting, elastic properties, non-destructive evaluation, ultrasonics

INTRODUCTION

The number of applications of advanced composite materials being employed in manufacturing constantly increases. But there still remain several obstacles which must be overcome before fibre-reinforced composites will be used exclusively in highly loaded primary structures. Foremost amongst these are: damage tolerance, delamination resistance and labor intensive manufacturing procedures. Many investigations have shown that the most effective way to improve the toughness and delamination characteristics of traditional two dimensional (2-D) laminates is through thickness reinforcement, eg. [1-5]. Applying cost effective textile processing technologies such as conventional stitching or needle-felting, the damage tolerance, delamination resistance and compression strength can be significantly improved. In general, the textile technologies used in the additional production step needed are very cost effective and do not dramatically increase the total manufacturing costs. Compared to the extensive data available describing the influence of these reinforcement techniques on the strength, fracture and fatigue behaviour of a large variety of materials, only limited data can be found in the open literature describing their influence on the stiffness properties of the final product, although they are equally essential for a material to find optimum application in design and production.

In this paper the influence of needle-felting on the in-plane and through thickness stiffness properties of fibre-reinforced laminates comprised of plain weave glass fabrics is studied. It was shown in [1] that the extremely fast and cost effective textile process significantly

improves the fracture and delamination characteristics of the material. The tensile stiffnesses in the plane of the laminate and the tensile and shear properties in the thickness direction of the material are determined in-situ by applying non-destructive evaluation techniques which were introduced earlier, eg. [6-8].

SPECIMENS

3-D Reinforcement by Needle-Felting

Needle-felting is a fast and cost effective process that can convert stacks of unidirectional prepreg laminates or woven fabrics into 3-D reinforced preforms in a single operation. The technique is considerably more economical than other methods of three dimensional reinforcement such as transverse stitching, weaving or braiding. In the needle-felting process a large number of individual, shaped needles are penetrating an aligned lay-up. The punching density in a one step operation may exceed 80 stitches/cm². The punching process forces fibres to bend out of the laminate plane which results in a 3-D fibre network. The manufacturing process is finished by infiltration of the preforms with matrix material and subsequent curing.

In the current investigation two square plates were tested. Both plates were comprised of four layers of glass fabric. The individual plies were woven from 3 mm thick fibre bundles in a plain weave pattern (Eifatex 19). The preform of plate B2 was punched with 80 stitches/cm² using a conventional needle-felting textile machine. Hot press curing using vacuum infiltration of the matrix material (Ciba Geigy LY556 Epoxy resin, HY917 hardener, DY070 accelerator) was used to manufacture the final laminates. The characteristic properties of the two sample plates are summarised in Table 1.

Improved Delamination Resistance

The influences of the needle-punching process on the mechanical properties of the materials and their microstructures have been reported earlier, [1]. The major results of these investigations are included in Table 1 and briefly summarised below.

Table 1: Characteristic properties of the glass fibre-reinforced square plates.

Specimen Notation		B1	B2
Material		four layers of roving fabric, unpunched	four layers of roving fabric, punched (80 stitches/cm ²)
Lateral Length L	[mm]	190	190
Mean Thickness 2H	[mm]	1.88	2.15
Fibre Volume Fraction	[%]	62	51
Density ρ	[g/cm ³]	2.10	1.92
In-plane Tensile Strength R_m	[N/mm ²]	480	370
Delamination Resistance G_{Ic}	[kJ/m]	1.0	5.0
Delamination Resistance G_{IIc}	[kJ/m]	0.8	3.9

Obviously, the needle-felting process changes the microstructure of the material. The 3-D reinforcement increases the volume of the preform. As a result, the thickness of the punched laminate is approximately 15% larger than the one of the unprocessed laminate, and the fibre volume fraction and the density of the punched material are smaller. An additional effect which contributes to these reductions is that air or gas is likely been trapped in the 3-D fibre network. Microscopical investigations have shown that the unpunched stacks of specimen B1 mainly feature individual, longitudinal gas inclusions which are located primarily between the laminate layers. In specimen B2 the total volume of the trapped gas is approximately twice as high. The inclusions are mainly round, their average diameter is approximately (0.5 ± 0.1) mm, and they are evenly distributed over the entire thickness of the laminate.

The results show that the mode I and mode II crack resistance of the 3-D reinforced laminates are approximately 5 times the ones of the unpunched material. As expected, the in-plane strength is slightly reduced due to the needle-felting process but an ultimate strength of 370 N/mm^2 is still sufficient for most technical applications using glass fibre-reinforced composites. The results for the needle-felting processed preforms are in good agreement with results for other, more expensive through thickness reinforcement techniques such as stitching, weaving or braiding.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Owing to the symmetry of the individual layers with respect to the laminate plane, six independent stiffness values are needed to describe the linear-elastic behaviour of the specimens. In the Cartesian coordinate system introduced in Fig. 1, these are: $E = E_{11}$, $E' = E_{22} = E_{33}$, $G' = G_{12} = G_{13}$, $G = G_{23}$, $\nu' = \nu_{21} = \nu_{31}$ and $\nu = \nu_{23}$.

There exist many static and dynamic measurement techniques to determine the elastic moduli of fibre-reinforced materials. In the current investigation the emphasis was on finding the tensile stiffness E in the laminate plane and the tensile and shear stiffnesses E' and G' in the direction of the thickness of the laminate. Therefore, two non-destructive, dynamic measuring techniques which have proven to allow for the accurate, in-situ determination of these stiffness components are used to quantify the influence of the needle-felting process, eg. [6 - 8]. The two techniques are briefly recapitulated below.

Flexural Waves

The tensile stiffness E in the plane of the laminate and the shear modulus G' in the thickness direction are determined by analysing the propagation behaviour of centrally excited flexural waves. The detailed derivation of the second order solution describing the propagation of flexural waves in an orthotropic material which is needed to analyse the experimental data, an extensive description of the measuring setup as well as an error propagation analysis can be found in [6]. Fig. 1 schematically outlines the measuring concept.

A piezoceramic transducer is used to excite a narrow band, ultrasonic pulse. From the displacement signals captured at distinct points along rays using a heterodyne Doppler laser interferometer, the phase velocity c as a function of frequency f or wavenumber k , ie. the dispersion curve, can be determined. Fig. 2 shows a measured dispersion curve for specimen B1 and B2, respectively.

Fig. 1: Measuring principle of the flexural wave experiments.

The locations of the piezoceramic transducer used as excitation source and the measuring points along the main axes of orthotropy were selected according to Fig. 3. With this setup, the measurement and model-related requirements may be met. Firstly, the narrow band excitation pulse can be separated from the reflections at the edges of the laminate. Secondly, the wavelength of the flexural waves are much larger than the characteristic lengths of the laminates. The resulting lower and upper limits for the centre frequency f_a of the excitation pulse are 40 kHz and 150 kHz, respectively.

Fig. 2: Measured dispersion curves for propagation along the principal axis x_2 , a) specimen B1, 587 data points, b) specimen B2, 533 data points.

Fig. 3: Selection of excitation location and measuring points (dimensions in [mm]),
1: excitation point, 2: measuring points, $\Delta x = 10$ mm.

Evaluation of the measured dispersion curves is based on the theoretical analysis of the propagation behaviour of flexural waves in an orthotropic plate, [6]. A perturbation method was used to derive the general, second order dispersion relation. For propagation along the principal directions x_2 and x_3 , we may write:

$$c \cong Hk \sqrt{\frac{E}{3\rho}} \left[1 + (Hk)^2 \frac{2E}{5G'} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

Point Source/Point Receiver Technique

The stiffness E' in the thickness direction was determined using a point source/point receiver (PS/PR) ultrasonic measurement technique, eg. [7, 8]. The setup is schematically outlined in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Schematic of the setup used in the PS/PR experiments.

Calculation of the stiffness is based on measuring the arrival time of a broad band excitation pulse. The group velocity c_p of the primary wave is calculated from the measured time of flight Δt and the distance between the excitation point and the receiver location. If the spring-

loaded receiver is mounted at the so-called epicentral location, ie. directly below the excitation point, the stiffness E' in the thickness direction can be determined using:

$$E' \cong \rho c_p^2 = \rho \left(\frac{2H}{\Delta t} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the case of the flexural waves the dispersion curves were determined using eight different centre frequencies f_a between 40 kHz and 140 kHz. Owing to the possibility of determining the phase velocity by analysing the signals captured at randomly selected measuring points along the principal directions x_2 and x_3 , twelve dispersion curves with respectively about 100 data points were determined for each laminate. The characteristic stiffness values E and G' are determined from these data points by non-linear regression using equation (1). Evaluation of the twelve dispersion curves for the specimens B1 and B2 affords the following values for the desired stiffness components.

Specimen B1	E = (36 ± 3) GPa	G' = (6.0 ± 0.5) GPa
Specimen B2	E = (31 ± 3) GPa	G' = (5.7 ± 0.5) GPa

The standard deviations greatly exceed the inherent accuracy of the measuring technique itself which was determined from an error propagation analysis, [6]. The reason is that the microstructure of the specimens produced by hot press curing using vacuum infiltration, considerably varies from point to point and consequently, the standard deviation of the determined stiffness values is large. Nevertheless, the mean values represent reliable quantities describing the global stiffness behaviour of the structures.

The needle-felting process has only a slight effect on the two stiffness components. Although the delamination resistance of the needle-punched laminate is a multiple of the conventional material, the stiffness values in the plane of the laminate are of the same order of magnitude. The considerable improvements in terms of crack resistance do not have a noticeable adverse effect on the in-plane tensile properties.

The test setup for the PS/PR experiments outlined in Fig. 4 makes it possible to easily collect data at various locations. Finding the average of all measurements thus affords values for the tensile stiffness E' .

Specimen B1	E' = (8.5 ± 2) GPa
Specimen B2	E' = (15 ± 3) GPa

As expected, the above mentioned inhomogenities turn out to have a considerable influence which results in large standard deviations. The mean values, however, definitely show that due to the additional reinforcement in the thickness direction, the tensile stiffness E' increases by about 70%.

CONCLUSIONS

Needle-felting of stacks of conventional glass textiles considerably improves the interlaminar properties of the laminates without having an appreciable adverse effect on the elastic properties. The tensile stiffness in the plane of the plate decreases by less than 10% while the tensile stiffness in the thickness direction increases by about 70%. The shear modulus G' in the direction of the thickness of the plate remains approximately constant. The needle-felting process seems to be an extremely cost effective method to produce toughness-optimised, glass fibre-reinforced fabrics whose in-plane elastic properties are not noticeably affected.

It remains to be elucidated whether this promising manufacturing process affords the same favourable results for aramide and also for carbon fibre-reinforced materials.

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